

INDEPENDENT COUNTERFACTUALS AND NECESSITARIANISM

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Counterfactual reasoning concerning singular events is often taken to involve the possibility that an event might not have occurred while the remainder of the world remains fixed. Under this view, some singular events are treated as isolated changes against an otherwise identical world. I argue that this assumption fails when combined with a causally deterministic view.

By causal determinism I mean the idea that, given the laws of nature and the total state of the world at any time, only one course of events can follow. On this view, the occurrence of any particular event is fully fixed by prior states together with the governing laws responsible for these states. If an event occurred, then the immediately preceding state of the world was sufficient, given the laws, to bring it about.

Suppose, then, that a singular event did not occur or occurred differently. Given determinism, this entails that the immediately prior state of the world must have been different, or else that the laws of nature must have been different. If the prior state was different, it follows that an earlier state must also have been different, since that state too was fixed by still earlier conditions. This reasoning may be repeated without a non-arbitrary stopping point, or, if one exists, until the initial state of the universe. Thus, if the event had failed to occur, the total prior history of the world would have had to differ. It follows that, under causal determinism, singular events cannot be counterfactually varied without altering the initial laws of nature.

This point extends recent criticisms of counterfactual isolation. A. Karofsky has argued that ordinary counterfactual reasoning often relies on background conditions that cannot coherently be held fixed, and that these conditions are frequently overlooked. On a causally deterministic view, however, the difficulty is not only one of conceivability. Any counterfactual requires changing all prior events, and consequently all subsequent events that follow from them. Treating singular events as contingent commits one to global contingentarianism of the universe, and more importantly, of its laws.

Historically, necessitarian philosophers such as Spinoza ground all events in an ultimate being, thereby avoiding the infinite regress of contingency.

Karofsky, A. (2021). *A Case for Necessitarianism*. Routledge.

Spinoza, B. (2002). *Ethics* (E. Curley, Trans.). London: Penguin Classics.